

Design of carry save adder using transmission gate logic

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ABSTRACT

In this paper Carry Save Adder has been implemented. The comparison is done on the basis of two performances such as area, power consumption. The full adder cells for low power applications have been implemented using transmission gate based technique for sum and carry operation. In this paper transmission gate also used. It used to minimize the transistor count. By using the transmission gate the transistor count has decreased thereby the total chip area gets minimized and the power consumption also gets reduced.

Keywords: Carry Save Adder, Full Adder, Power Consumption, and Transmission Gate.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the Very Large Scale IC (VLSI) applications, such as digital-signal processing and microprocessors, use arithmetic operations. In addition, among these widely used operations, subtraction and multiplication are most commonly used. The full adder is the building block of these operation modules. Therefore, enhancing its performance is crucial for ameliorating the performance of overall modules. Such an adder can be implemented using transmission gate technique. Among the logic styles available, transmission gate is found to enhance the circuit performance. Micro wind is a CMOS circuit editor and simulation tool for logic and layout-level design, running on Microsoft windows. It has been developed since 1998 through several versions, and is available as a freeware for educational purpose. In this paper, carry save adder based on transmission gate layouts are designed using Micro wind 2.7.

TRANSMISSION GATE LOGIC

The transmission gate is also known as pass gates represents another class of logic circuits which use TGs as basic building block. It consists of a PMOS and NMOS connected in parallel. Gate voltage applied to these gates is complementary of each other(C and Cbar). TGs act as bidirectional switch between two nodes A and B controlled by signal C. Gate of NMOS is connected to C and gate of PMOS is connected to Cbar(invert of c). When control signal C is high i.e. VDD, both transistor are on and provides a low resistance path between A and B. On the other hand, when C is low both are turned off and provide high impedance path between A and B.

PASS TRANSISTOR LOGIC

In PTL logic style gate and source propagates the signal. This logic style has a great functionality that can reduce the number of transistor counts. The pass transistor logic can be designed by either using pmos or nmos, but nmos is mostly desirable. This has low intermodal capacitance effects and therefore PTL enables low power and high speed digital circuits. Complementary pass transistor logic is pass transistor logic with complementary inputs and outputs. The pass transistors are used to design logic circuits. The pass transistor logic is used to minimize the chip area and power consumption of the circuit.

EXISTING SYSTEM:

With the Shannon's theorem the sum and carry expressions are condensed and thereby the transistor count has decreased. In the existing design of full adder the carry was generated using three AND gates and one OR gate whereas

the proposed full adder design uses only two transistors. Thus the area also gets minimized and thereby power has also been reduced to considerable amount.

$$C = (A \oplus B)B + (A \oplus B)C$$

In the existing design of full adder the carry was generated using one XOR gate, one XNOR gate two AND gates and one OR gate whereas the proposed full adder design uses only two transistors. Thus the area also gets minimized and thereby power has also been reduced to considerable amount.

$$S = (A \oplus B)\bar{C} + (A \oplus B)C$$

Fig 1: full adder circuit using gates

FULL ADDER USING TRANSMISSION GATES:

Fig 2: full adder circuit using transmission gates

The transmission function full adder, which uses 16 transistors for the realization of the full adder logic, is shown in Fig 2. This design uses pull-up and pull-down logic as well as complementary pass logic to drive the load. It has many advantages like low transistor count, low loading effect, better balancing between the signals than conventional full adder and it also exhibits high driving capabilities.

FULL ADDER USING PASS TRANSISTOR

The proposed full adder circuit has been designed using the pass transistor. The pass transistor circuit is used to reduce a transistor count. So the chip area has been minimized. The power dissipation has been reduced. In this paper 4 bit carry save adder (csa) has been designed using Shannon based full adder circuit. A carry save adder consists of a ladder of standalone full adders, and carries out a number of partial additions. Doing additions with carry save adder saves time and logic. In this method, for the first three numbers a row of full adder is used for each additional number. Then a row of full adder is added for each additional number. The final results, in the form of two numbers SUM and CARRY, are then summed up with a carry propagate adder or any other adder.

Fig 3: Shannon based full adder using pass transistor logic

PROPOSED SYSTEM

CARRY SAVE ADDER (CSA)

Basically, carry save adder is used to compute sum of three or more n-bit binary numbers. Carry save adder is same as a full adder. As shown in the Figure.4, here we are computing sum of two 4-bit binary numbers, so we take 10 full adders and two half adder. Carry save unit consists of 10 full adders and two half adder, each of which computes single sum and carry bit based only on the corresponding bits of the two input numbers. Let X and Y are two 32-bit numbers and produces partial sum and carry as S and C as shown in the Table1.

$$S_i = X_i \text{ xor } Y_i$$

$$C_i = X_i \text{ and } Y_i$$

The final addition is then computed as:

1. Shifting the carry sequence C left by one place.
2. Placing a 0 to the front (MSB) of the partial sum sequence S.
3. Finally, a ripple carry adder is used to add these two together and computing the resulting sum.

TABLE I. CARRY SAVE ADDER COMPUTATION

X:	1 0 0 1 1
Y:	1 1 0 0 1
Z:	0 1 0 1 1
<hr/>	
S:	0 0 0 0 1
C: +	1 1 0 1 1
<hr/>	
Sum:	1 1 0 1 1 1

Fig 4: Carry save adder for 4-bit number

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the results obtained from Synthesis and Simulation reports are presented. The aim of this experiment is to evaluate the performance of carry save adder on the basis of Area required, Speed of operation and power consumption. As shown in result CSA using transmission logic has shown better results than with CSA using logic gates. Area results are presented in terms of number of gate count required for implementing design on layout. CSA requires less CLBs because it requires less number of full adders. Further, simulation result shows that adder with CSA takes less time to generate final product because addition is performed in parallel without waiting for the previous result in case of CSA. Similarly, result shows slight improvement in power consumption in case of adder using CSA. Power

consumption depends on the switching activities. Therefore power consumption is directly proportional to area covered by the design on chip.

FULL ADDER USING LOGIC GATES LAYOUT DIAGRAMS

Simulation output

Full adder using pass transistor logic layout diagram

Simulation output

Full adder using transmission gate layout diagram

Simulation output

Carry save adder using transmission gate

Simulation output

COMPARISION TABLE

	NO OF MOSFETS	POWER CONSUMPTION
FULL ADDER USING GATES	54	36.358uw
FULL ADDER USING PASS TRANSISTOR	18	8.328uw
FULL ADDER USING TRANSMISSION GATE	16	3.353uw
CARRY SAVE ADDER USING TRANSMISSION GATE	172	46.272uw

CONCLUSION

The proposed CSA with transmission gate logic using full adder cell has been simulated. The main aspects are compared by power consumption and transistor count. The proposed carry save adder cell is having improvement in all these aspects. As shown in result CSA using transmission gate logic has shown better results than with CSA using logic gates. Area results are presented in terms of number of gate count required for implementing design on layout.

Referenes

- [1]HasanKrad and AwsYousif Al-Taie, "Performance Analysis of a 32-Bit Multiplier with a Carry-Look-Ahead Adder and a 32-bit Multiplier with a Ripple Adder using VHDL", Journal of Computer Science 2008.
- [2]. Z. Abid, H. El-Razouk and D.A. El-Dib, "Low power multipliers based on new hybrid full adders", Microelectronics Journal, Volume 39, 2008.
- [3].Nagendra, C.; Irwin, M.J.; Owens, R.M., "Area-time-power tradeoffs in parallel adders", Circuits and Systems II: Ana log and Digital Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on Volume 43, 1996.
- [4].Sertbas, A. and R.S. Özbey, " A performance analysis of classified binary adder architectures and the VHDL simulations". J. Elect. Electron. Eng., 2004.
- [5]. S.Saravanan,M.Madheswaran, "Design of low power, high performance area efficient Shannon based adder cell for neural network training,' Control, Automation, Communication and Energy Conversation,INCACEC 2009.
- [6]. J.D. Lee, Y.J. Yoony, K.H. Leez, B.-G. Park, "Application of dynamic pass- transistor logic to an 8-bit multiplier," J. Kor. Phys. Soc.38 (3) 2001.